

ON A CERTAIN INVERSE PROBLEM FOR CAROUSEL NUMBERS

Katsuya Mori

Hyogo Prefectural Takarazuka Higashi High School, Hyogo, Japan

katsuya-mori@hyogo-c.ed.jp

Received: 8/21/19, Accepted: 9/5/20, Published: 9/11/20

Abstract

It is well-known that for a special prime number p , a recurring period of $1/p$ defines a carousel number, and many such prime numbers have already been found. But the question as to whether there exists a carousel number not defined by any prime number has remained an open problem. In this paper, we prove that every carousel number appears in a recurring period of $1/p$ for a suitable prime number p . This is done by connecting the theory of recurring decimals and the theory of modular exponentiation.

1. Introduction

It is well-known that for a special prime number p , a recurring period of $1/p$ has a cyclicity. The smallest prime number which has such a cyclicity is 7. Let us represent $1/7$ by the recurring decimal:

$$\frac{1}{7} = 0.\dot{1}4285\dot{7}.$$

We multiply a recurring period 142857 of $1/7$ by $1, 2, \dots, 6$ and summarize the result in Table 1.

	1	4	2	8	5	7
$\times 1$	1	4	2	8	5	7
$\times 2$	2	8	5	7	1	4
$\times 3$	4	2	8	5	7	1
$\times 4$	5	7	1	4	2	8
$\times 5$	7	1	4	2	8	5
$\times 6$	8	7	1	4	2	8

Table 1

Table 1 reveals that 142857 has a cyclicity.

In general, for integers c_1, c_2, \dots, c_l such that $l \geq 2$ and $0 \leq c_1, c_2, \dots, c_l \leq 9$, we call a sequence $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$ a *carousel number* if for any natural number i such that $2 \leq i \leq l$, there exists a natural number j such that $2 \leq j \leq l$ and $i \times c_1c_2 \cdots c_l = c_jc_{j+1} \cdots c_l c_1 \cdots c_{j-1}$. Also, we call a prime number p a *carousel prime number* if the recurring period of minimum length which appears in the recurring decimal of $1/p$ defines a carousel number. The previous discussion indicates that 7 is a carousel prime number. It is well-known that p is a carousel prime number if the recurring period of minimum length which corresponds to p has length $p - 1$. By this fact, we can easily check that the other carousel prime numbers which are less than 100 are 17, 19, 23, 29, 47, 59, 69, and 97. While a large number of carousel prime numbers have already been found, it is not yet known whether there are infinitely many carousel prime numbers. It has also been an open problem to determine whether every carousel number is defined by a carousel prime number, therefore we solve this question in this paper.

The plan of this paper is as follows. In Section 1, we prepare notation and some well-known facts about recurring decimals. In Section 2, we show that every carousel number is associated with a prime number. In Section 3, we prove that for every carousel number there exists a carousel prime number p which defines the carousel number by employing the connection between the theory of recurring decimals and the theory of modular exponentiation. Furthermore, we prove that the length of the carousel number equals $p - 1$.

2. Preparation

We call an infinite recurring decimal *pure* if its recurring period starts from the first decimal place. In this paper, we consider only recurring decimals which are pure. Let n, k , and k' be natural numbers such that $n \geq 2$, $1 \leq k, k' \leq n - 1$, $(n, k) = 1$, and $(n, k') = 1$. First, let us begin with a basic fact about the length of a recurring period.

Lemma 1. *The recurring decimal of k/n has a recurring period of length l if and only if $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$.*

Proof. If the recurring decimal of k/n has a recurring period of length l , then $10^l k/n - k/n$ is an integer. Since $(n, k) = 1$, we have $10^l - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$, namely $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$.

Conversely, let us assume that $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. We see that $10^l k/n - k/n$ is an integer and thus decimal parts of $10^l k/n$ and k/n are the same. This shows that $10^l k/n - k/n$ is a recurring period of k/n and the length of it equals l . \square

In what follows, we study only recurring periods of minimum lengths. By Lemma 1, we see that the lengths of recurring periods of k/n such that $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$ and

$(n, k) = 1$ are the same and they are the smallest natural number l which satisfies $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. Next, we show a criterion for pureness of a recurring decimal.

Lemma 2. *The recurring decimal of k/n is pure if and only if $(n, 10) = 1$.*

Proof. If the recurring decimal of k/n is pure, then $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ by Lemma 1. Thus there exists an integer a such that

$$10^l - 1 = an.$$

This shows that $(n, 10) = 1$.

Conversely, assume that $(n, 10) = 1$. Clearly k/n does not define a finite decimal. If the recurring period of k/n does not start from the first decimal place, then there exists a natural number i such that

$$10^{i+l}k/n - 10^i k/n$$

is an integer. By our assumption, we see that

$$10^l k/n - k/n$$

is an integer and it shows that the recurring period of k/n starts from the first decimal place. This is a contradiction. \square

For recurring periods of k/n and k'/n , we consider that they are equivalent if they coincide by rotations of numbers each other and write $k/n \sim k'/n$. We can see that $k/n \sim k'/n$ if and only if there exists a nonnegative integer i such that $10^i k/n - k'/n$ is an integer, in other words, $10^i k \equiv k' \pmod{n}$. Let us denote by e the number of equivalence classes of recurring periods of k/n such that $1 \leq k \leq n-1$ and $(n, k) = 1$.

Lemma 3. $\varphi(n) = le$, where $\varphi(n)$ is Euler function.

Proof. Since k/n is pure, $(n, 10) = 1$ by Lemma 2. By Euler's theorem, we have

$$10^{\varphi(n)} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}. \tag{1}$$

Let Q and R be integers such that $0 \leq R < l$ and

$$\varphi(n) = lQ + R.$$

By (1), we have

$$10^{lQ+R} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}.$$

Since $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$,

$$10^R \equiv 1 \pmod{n}.$$

If $R > 0$, then this conflicts with the minimality of l . Thus we see that $R = 0$ and l divides $\varphi(n)$. It is clear that $e = \varphi(n)/l$ by the definition of e . \square

3. The Correspondence of a Carousel Number to a Prime Number

In this section, we discuss the recurring decimal of k/n which is associated with a carousel number $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$, namely

$$\frac{k}{n} = 0.\dot{c}_1c_2 \cdots \dot{c}_l.$$

We continue to use notation of the previous section. Our goal is to prove that n is a prime number. First, we prepare the following lemma.

Lemma 4. *The set $\{k, 2k, 3k, \dots, lk\}$ is invariant under multiplication by 10 modulo n .*

Proof. Since we assume that $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$ is a carousel number, there exist distinct natural numbers i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{l-1} such that

$$\begin{aligned} 2k &\equiv 10^{i_1}k \pmod{n}, \\ 3k &\equiv 10^{i_2}k \pmod{n}, \\ &\vdots \\ lk &\equiv 10^{i_{l-1}}k \pmod{n}, \end{aligned}$$

namely,

$$\{k, 2k, 3k, \dots, lk\} \equiv \{k, 10^{i_1}k, 10^{i_2}k, \dots, 10^{i_{l-1}}k\} \pmod{n}.$$

By Lemma 1 and the minimality of l we may assume that $1 \leq i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{l-1} \leq l-1$, and thus we see that the set $\{k, 2k, 3k, \dots, lk\}$ is invariant under multiplication by 10 modulo n . □

Now, let us prove the following result.

Proposition 1. *Let $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$ be a carousel number. If $k/n = 0.\dot{c}_1c_2 \cdots \dot{c}_l$, then n is a prime number.*

Proof. We assume that there exist natural numbers a and b such that $n = ab$, $a \neq 1$, and $b \neq 1$. First, let us discuss the case $a \leq l$ or $b \leq l$. Without loss of generality, we may assume that $a \leq l$. Since k/n is associated with a carousel number of length l , we have $k/n \sim ak/n$. Thus there exists a natural number i such that

$$10^i k \equiv ak \pmod{n}.$$

Since $(n, k) = 1$, we have

$$10^i \equiv a \pmod{n}.$$

This congruence relation shows that there exists a natural number j such that

$$a - 10^i = jab.$$

Rearranging this equation, we obtain

$$a(1 - jb) = 10^i.$$

Since the recurring decimal of k/n is pure, we have $(n, 10) = (ab, 10) = 1$ by Lemma 2. Thus we see that $2 \mid 1 - jb$ and $5 \mid 1 - jb$, namely, $10 \mid 1 - jb$ by comparing both sides of the above equation. Using induction, we see that $10^i \mid 1 - jb$, and thus we have $1 - jb = 10^i$. This shows that $a = 1$, but it conflicts with our assumption.

Next, let us discuss the case $a > l$ and $b > l$. Since $b \geq l + 1$ we have

$$l(l + 1) < ab = n. \tag{2}$$

By Lemma 4, we have

$$\begin{aligned} k + 2k + \dots + lk &\equiv 10k + 20k + \dots + 10lk \pmod{n}, \\ k \frac{1}{2}l(l + 1) &\equiv 10k \frac{1}{2}l(l + 1) \pmod{n}, \\ kl(l + 1) &\equiv 10kl(l + 1) \pmod{n}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(n, k) = 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} l(l + 1) &\equiv 10l(l + 1) \pmod{n}, \\ 9l(l + 1) &\equiv 0 \pmod{n}. \end{aligned}$$

This congruence relation shows that there exists a natural number c such that

$$9l(l + 1) = cn. \tag{3}$$

By (2) and (3), we have $cn < 9n$, namely, $c < 9$. Observing both sides of (3), we see that c must be an even number, thus c must be equal to any of 2, 4, 6, and 8. Since $\varphi(n) \mid n - 1$, there exists a natural number d such that

$$n - 1 = d\varphi(n).$$

By Lemma 3, we have

$$n = dle + 1. \tag{4}$$

By substituting (4) for (3), we have

$$9l(l + 1) = c(dle + 1).$$

Arranging this equation, we obtain

$$9l^2 + (9 - cde)l - c = 0.$$

This equation shows that l is a root of the following quadratic equation of which coefficients are integers:

$$9x^2 + (9 - cde)x - c = 0. \quad (5)$$

If $c = 2$, then (5) must be resolved into factors as the following:

$$(x - 2)(9x + 1) = 0. \quad (6)$$

Let us compare the coefficients of (5) to those of (6). We see that

$$de = 13.$$

Also we have $l = 2$ by (6), thus (4) shows that $n = 27$. The length of recurring period of $1/27 = 0.\dot{0}3\dot{7}$ is 3 and this contradicts the fact that $l = 2$.

If $c = 4$, then (5) must be resolved into factors as one of the following:

$$(x - 2)(9x + 2) = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$(x - 4)(9x + 1) = 0. \quad (8)$$

Let us compare the coefficients of (5) to those of (7). We have

$$4de = 25.$$

Since d and e are natural numbers, this is a contradiction. Next, we compare the coefficients of (5) to those of (8). We have

$$de = 11.$$

Since $l = 4$ we have $n = 45$ by (4), and this contradicts Lemma 2.

If $c = 6$, then (5) must be resolved into factors as one of the following:

$$(x - 2)(9x + 3) = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$(x - 3)(9x + 2) = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$(x - 6)(9x + 1) = 0. \quad (11)$$

Let us compare the coefficients of (5) to those of (9). We have

$$de = 4, l = 2.$$

This shows that $n = 9$, but the length of recurring period of $1/9 = 0.\dot{1}$ is 1 and this contradicts the fact that $l = 2$. By comparing the coefficients of (5) to those of (10) and (11), we have the following respectively:

$$6de = 34,$$

$$6de = 62.$$

Since d and e are natural numbers, these are contradictions.

Finally, let us look at the case $c = 8$. Equation (5) must be resolved into factors as one of the following:

$$(x - 2)(9x + 4) = 0, \tag{12}$$

$$(x - 4)(9x + 2) = 0, \tag{13}$$

$$(x - 8)(9x + 1) = 0. \tag{14}$$

Let us compare the coefficients of (5) to those of (12) and (13). We have the following respectively:

$$8de = 23,$$

$$8de = 43.$$

Since d and e are natural numbers, these are contradictions. Equation (14) shows that

$$de = 10, l = 8.$$

This shows that $n = 81$. But the length of the recurring period of $1/81 = 0.0\dot{1}234567\dot{9}$ is 9, this contradicts the fact that $l = 8$. \square

4. Main Result

In order to prove our main result, we establish the next proposition, which connects the theory of carousel numbers to the theory of modular exponentiation.

Proposition 2. *Let p be a prime number such that $p \neq 2, 5$. If $1/p \sim k/p$, then k is an eth power residue modulo p . Conversely, if k is an eth power residue modulo p , then $1/p \sim k/p$.*

Proof. If $1/p \sim k/p$, then there exists a natural number i such that

$$10^i \equiv k \pmod{p}. \tag{15}$$

Let r be a primitive root modulo p and j be a natural number such that

$$r^j \equiv 10 \pmod{p}. \tag{16}$$

Since $r^{jl} \equiv 10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ by Lemma 1, we have

$$p - 1 \mid jl.$$

Thus there exists a natural number j' such that

$$jl = (p - 1)j'.$$

By Lemma 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} jl &= lej', \\ j &= ej'. \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Equations (15), (16), and (17) show that

$$k \equiv 10^i \equiv (r^j)^i \equiv (r^i)^{ej'} \equiv (r^{ij'})^e \pmod{p}.$$

Conversely, we assume that k is an e th power residue modulo p . There exists a natural number i such that

$$k \equiv i^e \pmod{p}.$$

By Lemma 3 and Fermat's little theorem, we have

$$k^l \equiv i^{le} \equiv i^{\varphi(p)} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

Therefore we see that k is a root of the following equation:

$$x^l \equiv 1 \pmod{p}. \tag{18}$$

On the other hand, by Lemma 1 we have $10^l \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Thus we see that the following are distinct roots of (18):

$$1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, \dots, 10^{l-1}.$$

Since (18) has at most l roots, we see that there exists an integer j such that $0 \leq j \leq l - 1$ and $k \equiv 10^j \pmod{p}$. □

Finally, we shall prove our main result.

Theorem 1. *For any carousel number $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$, there exists a carousel prime number p which defines $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$. Furthermore, the length of $c_1c_2 \cdots c_l$ equals $p - 1$.*

Proof. By Proposition 1, we may put $k/p = 0.\dot{c}$ for a suitable prime number p . Since it is pure, we have $p \neq 2, 5$ by Lemma 2. Our assumption suggests that

$k/p \sim 2k/p \sim \dots \sim lk/p$. Since $k/p \sim 2k/p$, there exists a natural number m_1 such that

$$10^{m_1} k \equiv 2k \pmod{p}.$$

Since $(p, k) = 1$, we have

$$10^{m_1} \equiv 2 \pmod{p}.$$

By similar arguments, we see that there exist natural numbers m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{l-1} such that

$$\begin{aligned} 10^{m_2} &\equiv 3 \pmod{p}, \\ 10^{m_3} &\equiv 4 \pmod{p}, \\ &\vdots \\ 10^{m_{l-1}} &\equiv l \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

These congruence relations show that $1/p \sim 2/p \sim \dots \sim l/p$. By Proposition 2, we see that $1, 2, \dots, l$ are e th power residues modulo p . Now we assume that $e \geq 2$. $2l$ is a e th power residue modulo p and $l < 2l \leq el = p - 1$. This contradicts Proposition 2. Thus we see that $e = 1$ and $k/p = 1/p$. By Lemma 3, we can see that $l = p - 1$. \square

Acknowledgements. The author would like to express his appreciation to his students H. Inoue and R. Ito. Through joint research with them, he was introduced to this work. He also wishes to thank B. Landman and the referee for their sincere advice. Last but not least, he would like to give his sincere thanks to his family for their continued support during this work.

References

- [1] H. Inoue, On a regularity of a certain class of prime numbers, *J. and Proc. Young Archimedes* **2(2)**, (2016), 7–10.
- [2] R. Ito, A generalization of a symmetry related to a certain class of prime numbers, *J. and Proc. Young Archimedes* **3(1)**, (2018), 1–5.
- [3] G. Klatt, *carousel Numbers. A Lead-in to Number Theory*, <http://mathforum.org/orlando/klatt.orlando.html>, accessed 19 May 2014.